

Muftk: A Continuous Non-Equilibrium State Motion in Novel Mechanical Interaction Mechanism: A Groundbreaking Approach to Achieve First Cause Motion in Fuel Free Engine

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Abstract

Scientists are desperately looking for a new engine and trying big improvements in different engine types to fulfil future needs of world. This Engine is completely new only I have worked on it and I am launching it for first time at this level. It is Exploring the potential of novel mechanical interaction between two specifically shaped wheels. There is harvesting of motion from condition of non-equilibrium state dropping continuously in to non-equilibrium state ultimately achieving dynamic equilibrium in rotation of both wheels. This continuous non-equilibrium state is generating first-cause interactive motion named Muftk, while this motion is creating a new discrete Mechanical interactive force which is active force in the fuel free engine.

Keywords

Continuous non-equilibrium state propulsion, Novel Mechanical Interactive Motion, Discrete active force Generation, Novel Fuel Free Technology 2024, Generation of First cause motion, Novel Sustainable energy Technology 2024, Novel Engine invention 2024

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Research paper seems too lengthy 58 pages of description?

It is 17 years of work and it is Description of completely new engine.

Please, print and analyze description from page 1 to 30, It is written to prove existence and basics of Engine.

From page 31 to 52

All types of Muftk part contains short explanation of 7 out of 8 types.

From page 53 to 58

It contains some old rough notes of simple and slow version of machine.

It is not suitable to make multiple subscriptions in preprint and I want to transfer all novel data in one attempt. So, engineers can start thinking of machine by themselves.

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INTRODUCTION

“Non equilibrium state dropping continuously into non equilibrium state to achieve dynamic equilibrium in Fuel Free Engine”

Yes! No magnetism..., one hundred percent profile based mechanical interaction which is heart of fuel free engine.

Diagram no (1)

To describe about machine working diagram given is not representing actual dimensions, adjustments and shape. It is more like a strategy map.

When center of input wheel ‘**i**’ is pressed towards output wheel center ‘**o**’ with some mechanical technology all parts of device will come under stress. When pressure will be enough to throw system in non-equilibrium state, input and output both wheels will rotate coordinated. (input wheel will not drive any part of device for rotation).

Wheel interaction claim. In interaction both wheels have engaged each other at point **a**. If both wheel centers are compressed towards each other they will rotate on their place and interaction will slide from point **a** to point **c** by that rotation.

Question arises here... when compression is applied both wheel centers are supposed to move in direction of applied force towards each other by rotation. How are they just rotating on their own position?

Answer. It’s a bit tricky part. Both wheel centers are pushed towards each other but they are engaged on point **a**. In this way a triangular relationship between both wheel centers is developed.

The drop which we are expecting that **I** point will move towards **o** point is *adjusted* or it is happening in interaction zone. In other words, in interaction zone a rotating part of wheel *compensates* for this drop. Triangle keeps getting bigger and bigger. But in this way distance between **I** and **o** points is kept constant. So, both wheels rotate on their place.

The interaction is complex multi-dimensional and opportunity of *adjusting drop* is limited and it ends after limited degrees of rotation. This limited period can be repeated. During interaction both wheels rotate and by rotation similar pair of characters align to perform that period of interaction again in same way. In this way period by period 360-degree rotation is completed.

Conclusion

During interaction center of input wheel remains unmoved only with the respect of output wheel. Here “during interaction situation is changing but conditions remain same”. This mechanical logical interaction will happen in fuel free engine and will keep generating motion.

Now reader has two scientific norms. One is checking non-equilibrium state its target destination and non-equilibrium state on this place. Second is the adjustment of that distance in triangular relationship. Muftk is means “opened”. In equilibrium state everything is closed. Triangular relationship creating non-equilibrium state opens this closed state in to **Muftk** a novel fundamental mechanical interactive motion.

Non equilibrium state is an unbalanced state of body Which mathematically defines direction and force of body motion.

1 direction is defined by shape of body and relative conditions.

2 Non-equilibrium state will take force from equilibrium state and it is continuous velocity which is equal to mv .

(very important, please notice. *Initial velocity* is continuous velocity taken from equilibrium state, it is not a push or an input force. It is same feature as of basic interactions. Occurrence of force in unbalanced nature of bodies)

Body gets continuously unbalanced in this device, then “direction” becomes “path of motion” and “continuous velocity” becomes “constant velocity”.

Non equilibrium state is of two types translational and rotational. In this device algebraic sum of moments acting on wheels is not equal to zero. So, wheels are rotating only and their centers are not moving.

Dynamic equilibrium....

If parts of device drop from non-equilibrium state to non-equilibrium state continuously, they are in continuous unrest. The condition applies here. A body moving on a certain path with constant velocity achieves dynamic equilibrium.

Mechanical Device.... Now let’s play these conditions of dynamic equilibrium in a mechanical device. Assembly parts have certain, shape. Their relative interaction will result in continuous non equilibrium state.

Diagram no 1

PROVING MUFTK MOTION

Fuel Free Engine

Fuel free engine is a mechanical device which is using continuous non-equilibrium state to run. There is no combustion or alternative energy source processed in this Engine.

Interaction

Interaction is a term used for basic forces. I have used this word for “continuous unrest” expression for a basic relevance. In normal straight-line motion force is taken as input first then motion happens. It means force is first and then continue motion after it.

Interactions are forces exist with natural particles that are unbalanced with their relative particles. Unbalanced state has a natural tendency of keep moving until balance is found and this state will not ask you for force-input to move. Imagine a mechanical part is unbalanced with other mechanical part in a device it moves to target place and finds same unbalanced situation there, and this way on and on. It is condition of infinity. Motion in interactions comes first and force keeps on generating until particle or mechanical part is unbalanced.

Doubtless working

There is a doubt that may be an initial push for imbalance is an input. No, we compress center of wheel and wheel starts rotating. Despite of momentum transfer mechanical assembly have certain momentum deflecting properties active. Kind of mechanical logic.

For mechanical logic parts are adjusted with each other as they are left with only one possible way of working. To calculate constant non-equilibrium state, we just have to sum all forces acting in system. Once constant motion is confirmed we will get theory of Mechanical interaction.

Mechanical logic

Initial motion of two wheel's rotation is generated by the non-equilibrium state they share in their relationship. This period of non-equilibrium state can be extended when both special shaped wheels interact at certain non-orthodox angles keeping potential energy unchanged in system. In interaction zone a rotating part of wheel compensates for this drop by decoying drop its rotating part. In this way distance between both wheel centers is kept constant and potential energy is reserved. This period is complicated, complex and limited. It falls after some degrees of rotation. So, we invent device to adjust period after period to complete 360 degrees. This way constant rotation can be achieved and it is achieving dynamic equilibrium state in system.

Input Output Question

You have seen a heavy stone placed on land. If it is placed over rubber for long time it will decrease its elasticity. It means that in this condition stone didn't stop working on rubber. It is continuous velocity. This force does not quit working and needs no continuous input to keep its state. It is nature but when we come in mechanics there are many options which can increase continuous velocity enormously. For example, by using hydraulics. In this way we will use term of pressure for controlling input. Yes, input is pressure and output will be rotation in claimed device.....

It is simple, why wheel will rotate? Because it is in non-equilibrium state. To keep device out of balance we need pressure. The standard of input and output is just because we are defining a device otherwise continuous non-equilibrium state does not leave place for input output. Standard for device working is unbalanced state of interaction between wheels.

Now shape and arrangement and working of mechanical parts.

There are 8 eight types of Muftk here I am about to discuss one in complete detail while others in short detail will be adjusted separately in end.

Vertical to horizontal wheel type

In description when diagrams are simplified, I have ignored detail of third body (casing) which actually clings both bodies (wheels) and provides ground for compression tool (hydraulic etc.).

In the Diagram (1.1)

.....shown is that that two wheels are held together tightly in equilibrium. It means both wheel centers are moved towards each other with pressure. This force of vector X is continuous velocity and will change in to pressure N/sq m.

Both wheels get a compression force trapped in them it is not input now because system is in equilibrium state and there is no rotation. To rotate wheels, we shall not be driving them by rotating them.

In the Diagram (1.2)

It is shown that wheels are acting on one and another indirectly through a link. Both wheels will rotate to move that link out. There we can see formation of triangular force

relationship between wheels is rotating wheel. This is the simplest key to justify this motion. To use this out-ward motion of link in a better way we are in need to include some more details in features of these wheels. In this way we will get series of progressing triangular force relations for 'Muftk motion'.

Parts of Assembly

In the Diagram (1.3)

(Here we just want to prove mechanical motion exists. So, we will neglect description of complicated advanced features and accurate diagram dimensions, angles etc.)

It is named as vertical wheel because it works vertically in system. It has balled tip rollers on uniform distance along circumference line. It is almost like tip of ball point pen. This idea is not good against very high pressure and not strong but this roller can move all 360° degrees and it brings simplicity in description. These rollers can run on 'Hud' a grooved path on wedge. Here transverse cut section of groove is showing how it will prevent roller of vertical wheel from slipping out of groove on Hud. Vertical wheel has an axle. Holding this axle mechanism will press vertical wheel center on horizontal wheel surface.

In the Diagram (1.4)

Shown wheel is named Horizontal wheel because it works horizontally in system. It has wedges on one surface side, spread around on a uniform distance. Wedges are attached on horizontal wheel upright at 90° degree with respect to its surface. In this set up higher portion of wedge is directed towards center of horizontal wheel and they are located on radius line. (Actually, base of wedge is curved for smooth rotation. This curved is determined by riding angle. but as this cannot be handled in diagrams here it is kept straight. This description will be used to just prove possibility of motion).

In the Diagram (1.5)

.... Detail of wedge parts is given. Hypotenuse of this wedge is not straight it has curve and it is named 'Hud' a path of vertical wheel's roller to run on. The path Hud is inclining, to hold this path semi triangular structure wedge is formed. Here groove present on wedge adds in to feature of horizontal wheel. Whenever roller will try to slip over, groove will stop it, and groove will make roller move into it and gives rotation to horizontal wheel.

Hud is the path which is interaction path of both wheels during rotation. Displacement is base of that semi triangular structure wedge telling distance traveled, for better results we need to

curve displacement of wedge. Perpendicular of this wedge is height and it increases by travelling in groove. It is not possible to show wedge working in these diagrams. Therefore, we shall be drawing section of height only.

This section shows that both wheels are touching each-other on that height. In side view, movement will be shown as travelling from any lower height point section to higher height point section on displacement in both sides. And in upper view we can see displacement along radius line and where operating point is junction of both wheels.

So generally, these two things are happening at a time. One, roller of Vertical wheel is pushing wedge on horizontal wheel to rotate and as it rotates roller rolls to move in groove on Huda, and these things are not happening one by one both these things are happening together in same time.

Adjustment and Working of parts

In the Diagram (1.6) Adjustment of wheels is shown in side view.

Vertical wheel (V.W) is fixed vertically here. Restriction is a feature in casing that is slit kind of body restricting vertical wheel so it can rotate and move vertically downward or upward only. (This up or down movement is not said happening during working of logic). There is no ply in wheels and any such thing which is malfunctioning is not considered during machine working order.

Roller has engaged lower part of wedge on point 'C' on path 'Hud' which is shown by section of height 'h'. Horizontal wheel is fixed from center and free to rotate, its indication of rotation is movement of 'h' section in direction of 'Z' vector.

Non-equilibrium state

Most important thing you can see in side view and upper view and with both horizontal and vertical wheels is non-zero adjustment or non- equilibrium state. Vertical wheel is pressed down-ward with force shown by vector X, but horizontal wheel is not touching against center of wheel to oppose force equally. This non-zero situation can be evaluated to know result of forces on vertical wheel. Here magnitude of vector X is bigger than vector Z i.e. $X > Z$, here value of X is bigger than zero ($X \geq 1$). 'Z' is opposing force vector representing system inertia friction and utility work (e.g. generator) and it emerges to resist rotation of horizontal wheel.

Main logic work

We can resolve components of the force vector X which is acting through vertical wheel. ' C_x ' is a component of that force which is acting towards center of vertical wheel after interaction with ' h ' height section. Here ' C_x ' is opposed equally against input pressure. Restrictions are preventing sideways movement of vertical wheel so ' C_x ' becomes zero and center of wheel cannot move. ' C_y ' is tending to rotate vertical wheel and vertical wheel is clear for rotation.

' h ' height section on horizontal wheel is pushed downward where there is no way it can move. So, it will move vector ' Z ' and rotate horizontal wheel and vertical wheel with the force of vector ' C_y '.

We conclude from the diagram (1.6) side view that both wheels are rotating for one point and moving ' h ' section away.

In the Diagram (1.7) rotation of horizontal wheel is shown

This is upper view of horizontal wheel surface. In previous diagram side view section of wedge ' h ' height was shown, here section of wedge can be seen as a point on base or displacement of wedge crossing vertical wheel.

In this diagram vector X is engaging a point on wedge with the help of vertical wheel, this is height section ' h ' on wedge. let's see whether horizontal wheel is also clear for rotation. ' C_x ' is resolved vector of ' X ' which is acting towards fixed center of horizontal wheel. Value of ' C_x ' will be zero. Secondly ' C_y ' is acting to rotate horizontal wheel, as horizontal wheel is free to rotate so all vector magnitude shall be delivered to push and rotate horizontal wheel. By the push higher portion of wedge will slip under roller.

So, from diagram (1.7) upper view we conclude that both wheels are clear for rotation for a point and move ' h ' section away whereas in process expose relatively higher portion of wedge between wheels.

Rotation of period

Now it is obvious that non-zero adjustment is present in this mechanical logic. And whenever horizontal and vertical wheel will interact, they will rotate for every point under same conditions..... It is common sense if every point on wedge is clearing both wheels for interaction then both wheels will start interacting from lower part of wedge both will keep rotating and end interaction on higher portion of wedge.

Confusion Accepting Results

Despite reasonable many have hesitated accepting that both wheels will rotate. Top confusion is its result. When wheel gets support on higher portion of wedge after rotation then it means that both wheels will rotate on their place and their potential energy is not lost even after rotation. This result has proven very disturbing. Evaluators will keep accepting everything in 2d upper view and side view but when I will show them results of three dimensions, they seem to be like shocked and review description to find problems. But, No one can find any problem in 3d if they cannot find any problem in 2d. 3d is derived from 2d once it is clear there is no other way but to accept resultant 3d. Simplicity is always doubtless.

Simple diagrams confusion

One confusion is its simplicity. Diagrams are not calculated, especially wedge.... Wedge base will be curved and Hypotenuse will be curved also but they will be curved to fulfill the need of roller, to ease its movement. The size ratio and rotation difference of both wheels is also important factor in refining the shape of wedge. So, don't bother simple diagrams. Remaining issues can be resolved if you look for your answers.

It is important to note that mechanical logic is complex and multi-dimensional don't try to picture it in your mind holistically. Always rely on two dimensional diagrams when finding your answers. Look it in side view and upper view until you can clearly picture it in your mind. Thank you for giving time and focus for this part. This part is like everything for this paper.

In diagram (1.8)

In this diagram we will discuss a misunderstanding that vertical wheel is gaining height which is not possible. Some felt that it is like riding on a hill and it is not possible unless vertical wheel center gets a drop. Actually, what is happening here I should explain it with example of cartoon if you want car shown as moving forward in back ground trees are made to look moving backwards. Just keep focus and you will figure it out in end.

Well mechanical logic looks like touch and go but it's not that simple. In diagram no (1.8) roller moving in groove was at position P1 after rotation it's next position would be on P2. Dotted line is showing gain in height. Which is felt as not possible and wrongly drawn.

If a car has to put extra effort in going uphill it is because car is designed to run easily on straight leveled road. But look at vertical wheel its center is locked of motion so wheel will not

Roll. Whenever it will move it will Rotate on its place. So, if you can focus you will know that next height point is providing ground for wheel actually.

One-point Rotation

Consider one-point rotation of mechanical logic. Wheels were in non-equilibrium state and they rotated to find balance. What is the target place where vertical wheel's pin is supposed to be? Of course, in rotation on next height point. Wedge is designed to support and keep rotation and provide same non-equilibrium state on target place where wheel pin is going. If vertical wheel has to gain height then its center will be lifted against input vector X. So, we say that roller of vertical wheel is taking higher portion of wedge in act of rotation (not in act of gaining height).

Confusions of driven feelings

Normally a mechanical engineer has to deal with straight line motion in his life. So, they are used to the concept of one mechanical part driving other part..... A simple transfer of momentum. Mechanical Interaction is very new and complicated. It is not easy to digest that you have to put pressure (for creating non-equilibrium state) to drive rotation despite of putting in some initial driving force.

Just based on their feelings these critics try to reason like, no first vertical wheel center will move in direction of applied force. Vertical wheel will come down towards horizontal wheel and there will be rotation both wheels will rotate, potential energy will be lost and this is a wrongly assumed logic. But they don't have any reason to prove me wrong and prove them right.

From above discussion it evident that during this rotation vertical wheel center will not be moving down-ward in direction of applied force because increased height will support vertical wheel from underneath.

Mechanical logical behavior

In diagram (1.9)

Upper view is showing details of horizontal wheel rotation. We already know that higher part of semi-triangular structure wedge is present towards center of horizontal wheel and lower part is towards circumference line. As vertical wheel will push 'h' section on point 'a' it will move it. Then both wheels will rotate. By rotation we can see that rotating wedge will slide under vertical wheel on very next point 'b'. Although we can assume that very next point is nanometers like close but this diagram is made to give you a clear view that by rotation of both

wheels vertical wheel roller will reach on a new point 'b' to engage a new section of wedge of horizontal wheel. This is an important feature which makes this specific arrangement of wheels a mechanical logic every time a part of wedge is pushed new section gets set for the same rotation.

It is also obvious that 'b' point on wedge has a relatively higher portion of section 'h'. This next section 'h' is designed so precise that it gradually supports vertical wheel for needed height during rotation and does not let vertical wheel drop even a bit. There you can also see feasibility that higher portion of wedge is present at right side of vertical wheel. It has reasonable place to occur there and then roll under vertical wheel to other side. So, from diagrams (1.8) and (1.9) we learned that increase in wedge height and its rolling under vertical wheel is feasible.

In the Diagram (1.10)

Simplest way to judge motion is to consider motion on any point on path of interaction. If both wheels are clear for rotation on point a then b and c and all points between them, then both wheels are clear for rotation from interaction point a to c.

This diagram (1.10) shows that force relationship between two wheels is enough for rotation of both wheels from 'a' point to 'c' and any point between them. So, rotation will occur unless these points break their continuity.

We can see that there is an angle change of vertical wheel contact with wedge named riding angle. This angle changes the face of groove towards vertical wheel center by the change in height.

So, there is a vertical angle change by the change in height. One angle and one side of a triangle from vertical wheel.

In the Diagram (1.11) page no (8)

The upper view of horizontal wheel working is shown. Same kind of view as last diagram (1.10) here vertical wheel is pushing through points 'a', 'b' and 'c' rotating horizontal wheel. It is obvious that there is no opposing force against rotation. When wedge is pushed forward as a reaction with same force next part of high groove is forced under roller.

Riding angle

Here in diagram (1.11) we can see Riding angle. It is the angle of interaction between vertical wheel and wedge of horizontal wheel, we can see that this angle is more than 90° degrees. When this Riding angle will become equal to 90° degrees with diameter of horizontal wheel, there will be no interaction. It is just because of riding angle that after pushing for one-

point, vertical wheel gets an opportunity to keep riding on wedge. Riding angle is a must need for interaction. That is why this interaction can be continued within forth part of both wheels and we come up with a limited period of interaction.

So, in diagram (1.11), there is a horizontal angle change by the change in displacement. One angle and one side of a triangle from horizontal wheel. And it makes that during interaction of both wheels we can see two angle changes horizontal and vertical, by the change in base and perpendicular of semi triangular structure wedge.

Conclusion

This mechanical logic is enough to be seen from two side view and upper view. In both diagrams (1.11 & 1.12) it is obvious that all points from 'a' to 'c' hold feasibility to rotate both wheel and keep mechanical potential energy same through rotation.

Clearly if mechanical potential will remain constant in system mechanical kinetic energy will remain same also. But there is a latest line I have for this situation.

“If in a system, any of space, complexity or time becomes infinite absolute zero is achieved. While in this proposed Muftk motion space and complexity are infinite and time is irrelevant”. (Article introduction in reference of this statement is in last)

It is a genuine Mechanical Fundamental Interaction.

It is to be noticed in that rotation we can start from any point between 'a' and 'c'. On every point vertical wheel (vector X) is in touch to provide push for motion which is not ordinarily found in mechanicals.

This specific feature has given me reason to say that there is regeneration of motion throughout rotation and this mechanical logic will generate force in form of motion by continuous non-equilibrium state.

We conclude Motion has happened first and force is due to presence of motion.

Whereas in ordinary motion we can start from first point only, after that a body who has been given momentum uses this momentum until discharged of given energy. If we want to start motion after first strike point, we cannot get motion from there.

This is clear mechanical interaction. it has capability of regenerating motion on each point of rotation. this motion is discrete (regenerating same momentum value on each point of rotation).

So, here we can comment Muftk motion is discrete.

Diagrams no (1.12)

Here two series of diagrams are shown. Each series has three diagrams to show the progress of move. One series for Muftk motion from side view and one for an ordinary wheel rolling down-stairs. We can see drop of ordinary wheel when it is rolling down-stairs, so there is drop and rotation of wheel. This kind of drop and rotation can be seen in Muftk motion also and it can answer many questions by itself. There is shown some increase in distance, it is compensation of the travel, which wheel center was about to make by moving downward for rotation. Now wheel has rotated on its place and drop has been adjusted in this increased distance. So, at the end of the day it is a mechanical logic not a magician's illusion.

We should not be afraid of perpetual motion so much that it ceases our thinking and believing capacity. I have seen no idea in history of perpetual motion being proven mathematically so powerful. After all, as a research worker I want to say that if I were analyzing something like that, I will never throw it for assumptions.

Conclusion...

- Muftk motion is an exception and it doesn't fall against scientific norms.

It is end of a most important part of paper in which I have to prove that this motion has proper theoretical basics of existence. Remaining are 7 seven types they will be discussed them in short.

**Mechanical interaction
Diagrams**
(1.1) to (1.12) pages (9)

Drawing no (1.1)

Drawing no (1.2)

Diagram no (1.3)

V.W vertical wheel

Wheel axle

Balled tip

Tip holding ball as ball pen

Wedge transverse cut section fixed on H.W

Diagram no (1.8)

Diagram no (1.9)

Diagram no (1.10)

Diagrams no (1.12)

Muflk motion
Side view

Ball Rolling
downstairs

MECHANICAL INTERACTION

Presenting theory as a solution to any problem is a knockout win. But how anyone can explain perpetual motion working mathematically?

Here a concept of interaction comes in that “sometimes a force can be seen in an unbalanced nature of a body”. Precisely! we are about to Play Interaction in classical physics. Let's explain it in a way of comparison with natural interaction.

Take example of moon interaction with Earth. Relation between moon and earth is unbalanced. Every unbalanced situation keeps moving until it finds balance. Moon cannot drop into Earth and cannot move straight out of orbit. To come out of this situation Moon rotates around itself and shifts its place around Earth in orbit in order to seek balance but what it finds there is that same unbalanced state..... this is continuous unrest. In this way Moon achieves dynamic equilibrium state attains constant velocity and keeps moving in orbit around Earth like forever.

Interaction

To copy interaction in a mechanical device we will press two wheel centers towards each other. Complicated shape of wheels upon interaction will make both wheels rotate on their place.

First hit advantage of this arrangement is achievement of collision state. Both wheels will remain intact and rotate then there will be exemption from law of conservation of momentum, because to apply law of conservation of momentum bodies have to leave each other's contact with distributed energy.

.....bodies have magnetic field although we cannot see it but under certain conditions it behaves mechanically. So, if this magnetic field is replaced by some complicated metal shape then it is ultra-reliable, because we can calculate for super surety that what will happen when both wheels will interact.

Unbalanced

both wheels are pressed towards each other now they are acting unbalanced with respect to each other. Change word "unbalanced" with scientific term 'non equilibrium state' and now we can calculate it mathematically.

There are two conditions of non-equilibrium state. It can be rotational and translational. Here algebraic sum of moments acting on wheel is not equal to zero. So, this condition produces rotational velocity in device. Forces acting on center of wheel are equal to zero so there is no translational non equilibrium state. As a result, wheels are rotating on their place.

Same unbalanced state

whenever a body moves under non-equilibrium state it reaches some target place we can evaluate. If conditions are same 'unbalanced' on target place. Then we can say that wheels are dropping from non-equilibrium state into non equilibrium state continuously with respect to each other. So, wheels are rotating continuously.

Dynamic equilibrium

If this process of continuous unrest goes on. Then we can conclude that system of wheels has achieved dynamic state of equilibrium and wheels are rotating with constant velocity.

Constant velocity means if we are for example driving a generator with this device, it will not reduce energy in system. If the system is in continuous non equilibrium state it will keep moving, because of a discrete force Mechanical interactive force will become active in fuel free engine device.

Please note that system is producing motion here and energy is due to motion. Normally equation in classical physics is energy first and then motion while in interactions motion is produced first and energy is present due to motion. It is like entropy in classical physics.

Orbit

In interactions body follows a path which is repeated indefinitely keeping conditions unchanged. Moon follows path around Earth while in this device we just have to complete a 360-degree rotation and it can be repeated indefinitely.

Dynamics

All interactions are isolated and they have complicated dynamics. This device is kind of mechanically isolated. One wheel is taking its three coordinates and acting on another wheel and other wheel is not someone acted by or driven by, this wheel is also with its three dimensions acting on first one, an active collision-state. This situation is creating two frames of references in which active forces are trapped inside.

That is why I have used word of complexity. We human beings live in 3 dimensions and we can handle 2d easily so we normally make upper view and side view two diagrams and our mind joins them and reads them. Here complexity situation develops for human beings as our brains are not able to calculate and predict this interaction easily. So, complexity here is coming with certain results. Just because it is mechanical and we can see it so we can figure out how to calculate it. It is a hint that universe has certain patterns and it is not chaotic and random.

Animation software and AI

Mentioned these details to clarify that this interaction cannot be checked in any animation software. In same way this interaction either cannot be handled by AI artificial intelligence by means of concept and working.

Dynamics of normal motion can be simply explained as straight line motion. Body carrying energy. Whenever we are dealing with this motion, we use equation of input output to evaluate work done.

Input output cannot judge interactions. Now interactions have their own identity in classical physics. I have explained them under title

"non equilibrium state dropping continuously into non equilibrium state to achieve dynamic equilibrium in Mechanical interaction device".

In this condition an infinity is enough to realize that we are experiencing features of quantum mechanics in classical physics, an unbelievable phenomenon. Mechanical Interaction can be defined here also as...

“Mechanical Interaction happens when both bodies act on each other at right angle to their center of rotation”

This definition is defining a rule which has developed complexity. Machine kept this rule working against every possible change happened during rotation of both wheels. Mechanical shape passed every challenge came in its way and these challenges made its shape complex. This complexity became infinite and held space infinite with it. As Mechanical interaction mechanism is an isolated unit and is not a technical process so time is not relevant here.

“as complexity and space are infinite in this interaction so this unit is able to work infinitely forever until its shape remains unchanged”

It is something like a new fundamental force generator is developed.

Conclusion

"ability to do work is energy". As this device has ability to do work as long as it is in non-equilibrium state. So, we can conclude that device is a source of energy.

[Read me](#)

- History: logic idea came in my mind in Sep 2004, in mid-2005 I wrote it first time, in 2005 I gave first lecture in Sargodha Polytechnique, in 2007 claimed in newspaper that I have such technology basics, in 2008 applied for patent (feel free I will not claim for copy right & monopolize this technology), in 2012 presented technology in seminar, news of seminar was published in newspaper.
- This technology is a major upset of Industrial era. All alternative and sustainable technologies will be left at once. Most of the engine types will start to be eliminated and energy hunt of mankind will be over. Most important there will be no global warming problem. But there is a negative side many industries can go bankrupt and businessman can lose their capital. There is a solution for this condition. Banks will also face changes. There is need to redefine term GDP. Surely there are benefits of this technology which cannot be blindly converted in to printed paper (currency). Government should make policies to shift these benefits to people and stop this bankruptcy. An international term of renegotiation should be introduced for agreements. Many things can be done to make this upset a blessing.....
- There is an old update. It can be useful; it is its torrent link. Files will be shared on this torrent in case there is need.

magnet:?xt=urn:btih:55A17859478BD6B0CAB5E39496F2894568E9420B&dn=Fuel%20Free%20Engine%20pack&tr=udp%3a%2f%2ftracker.openbittorrent.com%3a80%2fannounce&tr=udp%3a%2f%2ftracker.opentracker.org%3a1337%2fannounce

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Absolute zero achieve

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Physicists Discovered a Quantum Trick For Reaching Absolute Zero

PHYSICS

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Ice-covered thermometer

(Erik Von Weber/The Image Bank/Getty Images)

The state of perfect stillness known as absolute zero is one of the Universe's impossible achievements. As close as we can get, the laws of physics will always prevent us from hitting thermal rock bottom.

An international team of researchers has now identified a new theoretical route to reach the mythical mark of zero Kelvin, or -273.15 degrees Celsius (-459.67 degrees Fahrenheit). No, it's not more likely to break any laws and remove every last shimmer of heat, but the framework could inspire new ways of exploring matter at low temperatures.

As a consequence of the third law of thermodynamics, the removal of increments of heat energy from a group of particles to cool them to absolute zero will always take an infinite number of steps. As such, it requires an infinite amount of energy to achieve. Quite the challenge.

Classical physics makes this relatively obvious. Viewed in the context of quantum physics, however, the problem begins to look a little different.

Quantum physics describes particles according to a spread of possibilities. Only once a feature is measured does it have a concrete state, and even then, other qualities of the particle become a little less certain. A particle at the theoretical point of absolute zero would have no movement, meaning its position would be certain. Quantum details regarding its prior position would effectively be wiped, deleting information.

Enter Landauer's principle, which states that deleting a piece of information requires a minimum and finite amount of energy.

Does that mean there is a quantum trick to dropping to zero after all?

There are two solutions to the paradox. An infinite amount of time or energy could still be required to make that leap. Or – as per the new research – it would require the deletion of an infinite amount of complexity.

It's this new revelation of the role of complexity that presents a new angle to the search for a pathway to absolute zero, even if it is as practically impossible as a solution as the ones scientists have already been working with.

"We found that quantum systems can be defined that allow the absolute ground state to be reached even at finite energy and in finite time – none of us had expected that," says particle physicist Marcus Huber, from the Vienna University of Technology in Austria.

"But these special quantum systems have another important property: they are infinitely complex."

What we now have is essentially a 'quantum version' of the third law of thermodynamics that goes beyond what classical physics teaches us: an infinite amount of energy, time, or complexity is required to get to absolute zero.

The calculations and modeling carried out by the team also show that the perfect erasure of data and the lowest possible temperature are closely linked, and both apparently impossible to achieve by we mere mortals.

It's possible then that increasing complexity in systems is another way of getting closer to absolute zero, or at least proceeding more quickly.

"If you want to perfectly erase quantum information in a quantum computer, and in the process transfer a qubit to a perfectly pure ground state, then theoretically you would need an infinitely complex quantum computer that can perfectly control an infinite number of particles," says Huber.

In practical terms, no computer system is ever perfect – so the idea that a particle in a quantum computer could never be fully wiped of its data (or previous states) shouldn't be a stumbling block in the development of these technologies.

Quantum mechanics and temperature are closely related – when we get close to absolute zero, strange quantum phenomena start happening – and the researchers say that this is another area where the findings of this study can be useful in the future.

"This is precisely why it is so important to better understand the connection between quantum theory and thermodynamics," says Huber. "There is a lot of interesting progress in this area at the moment. It is slowly becoming possible to see how these two important parts of physics intertwine."

The research has been published in PRX Quantum.

ALL TYPES OF MUFTK

Short Explanation

Muftk has different types. Details of Vertical to horizontal type are used for proving Muftk interaction. Remaining types and details are shortly explained in this file and this file is in continuity of previous one.

Pin and groove are categorized as characters in the explanation. This pair of pin and groove is simple and good for explanation but in real world of mechanics this pair is not feasible. We know that there is always a slight play in the wheel rotation. The level of accuracy for interaction is not possible to achieve with play. So, either we have to make big gigantic and slow machines or pin and groove should be replaced or modified.

We know magnetic levitation. In magnetic levitation both bodies are made to engage each other and both bodies have similar charge which repels each other so their contact is more like non-physical.

Diagram number 1

This diagram is a transverse cut section of pin and groove. As both bodies carry similar charge so there is a repulsion between them. If there is a play movement in pin due to the play in wheel then there is enough space to accommodate that play.

Rotation speed between wheel shall reach to possible maximum. Any slight collision between parts at this speed will result in destruction of whole device.

The space will prevent any kind of collision. There will be a cloud of levitation force between both pin and groove. This cloud of force will also design path and will prevent play of wheels.

The cloud of levitation force is EMF due to the current most probably super conductive. If direction of that electric current is also controlled to run in similar direction and synchronized properly. This factor will also contribute fairly in preventing collision between wheels and giving some super speedy momentum. This modification will increase the ability of making big amount of electric current of this device at the level of super conductivity.

Super conductive environment will control temperature changes, continuity of electric current and amount of electric current. These factors will contribute to stable EMF in device which is good enough for working of this machine. Pin will be moving through designed path of EMF.

Diagram number 2

Shapes are perfectly designed to increase surface area between both wheels. Here we can make pin in form of a tabloid and shape grooves accordingly.

Diagram number 3

This diagram is giving idea of carving tablet pin in case it has to move through a bit curved groove. These are some basic inventive steps to make this device work with levitation. When it comes to designs there is a big number of possible and good designs one can make. With the use of levitation engine will run at super speed and will be able to produce large amount of electric current.

Basic components

In Muftk interaction can happen between a pair of basic components. Basic component is simplified mechanical part. They are

Diagram number 4

In this diagram vertical wheel is shown. Vertical wheel interacts vertically in system at 90° but this angle can be unorthodox. This angle can be tilted somewhere near 45 degrees but wheel will be applying force from center and engaging with circumference. Characters like pin or groove will be placed on circumference line.

Diagram number 5

Diagram number five is showing horizontal wheel. This wheel works horizontally in Muftk system. During interaction surface area is engaged. Characters like pin or grooves are placed on side surface area of this wheel.

Diagram number 6

This diagram is showing ring wheel. Ring wheel interacts using inner circumference side as shown in figure.

Diagram number 7

Diagram number 7 is showing slider. Slider is a rectangular body which moves to and fro during interaction. It can have wedges or pins on a side surface.

There are components of pipes type but they will be explained at the end after explanation of all types.

These basic components pair with each other to form the different types of Muftk interaction. These different types are

1. Vertical wheel to horizontal wheel.
2. Vertical wheel to vertical wheel.
3. Vertical wheel to slider.
4. Vertical wheel to Ring Wheel.
5. Ring Wheel to slider.
6. Ring Wheel to Ring Wheel.
7. Ring Wheel to horizontal wheel.
8. Pipes type.

Vertical wheel to horizontal wheel.

This type is already been explained in detail previously in order to prove interaction.

Vertical wheel to vertical wheel.

Diagram number 8

This diagram is showing interaction between two vertical wheels. First thing to notice is its non-zero adjustment. Both wheels are touching each other in a way that no wheel gets equilibrium state. Wedges are adjusted crosswise. If wedges are straight on vertical wheel then angle off interaction between both wheels should not be 90° as shown in diagram number 10. The engagement is always an un-orthodox to achieve non-zero state of equilibrium between basic components.

It is upper view and we can see that upper vertical wheel is engaging lower vertical wheels wedge on point a. When upper vertical wheel is pressed towards lower vertical wheel both wheels will rotate. In this diagram we can see lower vertical view is clear for rotation.

Diagram number 9

This diagram is showing vertical wheel to vertical wheel interaction from side view. Upper vertical wheel is pressed on wedge of lower vertical wheel on point a as a result both fields rotate and point of interaction will move from a to point b and c. So, upper vertical wheel is also clear for rotation.

Vertical wheel to Slider

Diagram number 11

This diagram is showing vertical wheel to slider from upper view. Vertical wheel is engaging wedge on point a. When vertical wheel is compressed it will move slider. Slider cannot move in direction of vertical wheel because it is restricted to move right or left. So, it will move sideways.

This type is very similar as vertical to vertical wheel interaction. Movement of upper vertical wheel from side view is a lot similar.

Vertical wheel to ring wheel

Diagram number 12

This diagram is showing vertical wheel to ring wheel interaction from side view. This interaction is very similar to vertical to vertical wheel and slider. Vertical wheel is compressed on point a, it moves wedge sideways and rotation occurs in both wheels.

Diagram number 13

This diagram is showing vertical wheel to ring Wheel interaction from upper view. Here it is Shown in an unorthodox way. Conventionally this interaction can happen crosswise at approx. 45 degrees just like operating slider.

Vertical wheel is engaging ring Wheel at point a. On compression both wheels will rotate and point of interaction will travel from point a to point b and then c.

Ring wheel to Slider

Diagram number 14

This diagram is showing interaction of ring wheel with slider upper view.

Ring wheel is compressed on slider. Engages sliders wedge on point a, as ring wheel pin will travel in groove of wedge slider will move sideways and a period of interaction will happen.

Ring Wheel to Ring Wheel

Diagram number 15

This diagram is showing interaction between pair of ring wheels from side view. Centers of both wheels are not acting towards or against each other to avoid equilibrium state. Angle between both wheels is not absolute 90 degrees.

Upper vertical wheel has engaged lower ring Wheel on point a on lower part of wedge. When compression is applied this interaction will travel through groove on point c.

From this view we can see rotation of lower ring wheel.

Diagram number 16

This diagram is showing ring wheel to ring wheel interaction from upper view. In this type of interaction both wheels kind of overlap each other. Upon compression both wheels will start interaction from point a and will end on point c.

Ring Wheel to horizontal wheel

Diagram number 17

This diagram is showing Ring Wheel to horizontal wheel interaction from side view. Horizontal wheel is looking like ring wheel but you can tell it by the wedge which is on side surface of wheel. Both wheels will start interaction from point a, upon compression both wheels will rotate and point of interaction will reach on point c. Ring is clear for rotation in this view.

Diagram number 18

In this diagram we can see ring wheel to horizontal wheel interaction from upper view. In this view we can see rotation of horizontal wheel. Both wheels will start interaction from point a and end on higher part of wedge point c.

pipes type

Diagram number 19

In this diagram pipes type of Muftk interaction is discussed. Pipe is cut at an angle.

Diagram number 19a

In the diagrams a condition of pipes is discussed to get an idea how this combination will work in assembly. It starts from when pipes are closed. One pipe is fixed and the second pipe is rotatable. Rotatable pipe has a pin which is when rotated it rotates the pipe. In diagram 19a two cut pieces are meeting as they are full uncut pipes.

Diagram number 19b

In this diagram pipes are opened and there is increase in length of pipes. When pin is rotated it will rotate one of the pipes and the shape after rotation will increase length of pipes.

Diagram number 20a

In this diagram pipes type assembly is explained where pipes will work. Generally, it is a triangular adjustment. There is a device ground. This triangle has three corners a b and c. a and b joints are rotation able joints while c has a restriction of movement it can move horizontally back and forth only. Whenever point c will change its position all angles of triangle will change.

Diagram number 20b

This diagram is showing installment of pipes in triangular structure. Non rotation able pipe will take corner of a. Rotational pipe will take corner of c. There is a pin with rotation able pipe this pin will engage with a pole on the ground base of triangular frame.

Diagram number 21

Previously simplified assembly was explained, here in this diagram pipes type motion is explained.

Downward compression is applied from the corner of point a. When compression will be applied on point a the only loose corner c will travel. When point c will travel pin attached with rotation able pipe will entangle with pole on ground of assembly. This pole will rotate and with it rotation able pipe will rotate also. When rotation able pipe Will rotate length between point a and c will increase.

With the increased length of one side ac, a new triangle will happen. The distance between ground and point a will remain unchanged in this new triangle which is an exception.

Types of Mufthk interactions

Diagram no 4
Vertical wheel (VW)

VW interaction place

Diagram no 5
Horizontal wheel (HW)

HW interaction place
Side surface

Diagram no 6
Ring wheel (RW)

RW interaction place
inner surface

Diagram no 7
Slider

Slider interaction place
Side surface

Diagram no 10
Unorthodox VW to VW
Interaction.

Diagram no 11
Slider to VW
Upper view

One side of slider can
be slightly down

Slider movement

Engaging lower
wedge part

Vertical wheel from
upper view

Diagram no 12
VW to RW
Side view

Diagram no 14
RW to slider
Upper view

Engaging lower
wedge part
On slider wedge

Slider movement

RW rotation

Diagram no 16
RW to RW
Upper View

In Muftk interaction wheels or basic components never interact on absolute 90 degree if it is then sometimes wedges are adjusted diagonally.

Diagram no 17
RW to HW
Side view

Diagram no 18
RW to HW
Upper view

Diagram no 19
Pipes type

Diagram no 19a
Closed pipes

Diagram no 19b
Opened pipes

Diagram no 21
Pipes type motion

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Muftk Characters

Characters are physical objects in basic logical components. Their shape defines them individual but their purpose is to facilitate interactive motion between basic logical components. They are discussed here to make simple designs of Muftk possible. Magnetic levitation is not possible to make right away. These old designs are easy and feasible to make initially. They have different types in pairs for example.

Grooved wedge and roller and Grooved wedge and sledge.

Wedge

Wedges are semi triangular structures attached with basic components, providing slide for rollers attached on another component. They serve smooth interaction between basic components as featured shape.

Diagram no. (1) & (2)

Wedge has groove it is made for roller or sledge on Huda which is supported and curved to face and fit them by rotation. This groove runs over Huda and changes by change in height and displacement. In diagram (2) the condition is displayed for an instant.

Paired wedges have difference in working which differs by logic. Wheel's wedge is a simplest type of wedge. It works by the rotation of wheel whereas slider wedge works by the slide both the wedges deal with vertical and horizontal angle change at a time. In pipes logic this job is divided in two wedges. A wedge deals with motion on vertical axis whereas another circular wrapped wedge supports displacement in rotation.

Sledge or Roller

A sledge or roller work with wedge when they are attached with basic components. They counter with angle changes and resistance to roll over Huda.

All the characters can have various changes to work in efficient and aimed manner. These changes are in fixation, shape and techniques.

1) Inversion of wedge

In the Diagram (3)

For Muftk we can engage any fourth part of basic component's rotation that is less than of 90° rotation working over fourth part of other basic component. As Qatar has direction, if distance of Qatar is increasing from circumference line point to point then higher portion of resultant wedge 'H' will be traveling in to circle for this it is said as Qatar in (Q.I). If this distance is decreasing Qatar out (Q.O) then lower portion 'L' will be faced inward. Wedge gets inverted in case of Qatar out when we are getting out of rotation, this formula affects nearly every type of Muftk and adds 'inverted wedge' in name of logic.

We can jointly use straight and inverted wedges both in vertical to horizontal mechanical interaction. It is unified wedge.

Diagram (3) in this technique motion continues from one fourth part of circle to another. It gives a long period and roller director method is used with it.

2) Exchanging characters.

In exchanging characters character pairs interchange their places on basic components. This interchanging does not affect mechanical logic. All basic components can have wedged groove or roller or sledge as character pair. Most of possible shapes are defined already in other descriptions as rolled or wedged vertical wheel; roller or sledge on slide is simple fixation moreover basic components can also switch. You can make fix rotary anyone and other center can be moveable and operating.

Shape of Characters

3) Concave convex pair

Concave groove convex roller

In the Diagram (25) page ()

We shall calculate a 'Height' and an 'angle' of vertical rotation on a specific displacement point for 'Huda' and for this point on 'Huda' we can design assembly as simple concave groove on wedge and rolling surface of roller is simple convex, this type is typical and favorite in normal conditions.

Concave roller convex groove

In the Diagram (26) page ()

4) *Roller director method*

For horizontal rotation we can add another roller, which can direct rolling direction of roller. It is situated behind or before roller and we can improve a wall on a side of groove for it to work roller director his way as shown in diagram no. (33 &34) page no. ().

This is roller director method. In this way roller director touches wall and directs roller on wedge. It is a slow system to operate wedge by roller because it adds another process in working.

5) *Fixed angle rolling*

Fixed angle rolling is fixation of roller on a certain horizontal angle. In this method we cannot make long groove but complication is minimized. displacement of wedge is curved to serve fixed roller of vertical wheel.

Application of fixed angle rolling for curved displacement technique. "If roller is touching any point on wedge then direction of next point is determined by rolling direction of roller".

6) *Double touch*

Double touch (or Multi touch) is a technique, which is effective against unsafe moment on the first hand when one period is over and next roller is about to pair with next wedge. In this next roller is fixed to pair with next wedge before the first pair leave. In this way Wheel is working over more than one wedge at a time. This method gives more surface area as intersection points between basic components so there is capacity to increase pressure in system.

7) *Bumpy motion*

There are three possible scenarios in adjusting Huda (the hypotenuse of wedge). We can design it to keep distance between both wheels unchanged. We can also design this Huda to increase and decrease distance between both centers.

In the Diagram (1) page no ()

Up and down motion of free basic component evenly is bumpy motion it depends on material nature that is applying pressure on system for its power and is made by changing path Huda on wedge for ups and down as extended Huda of even motion. For this path wheel will punch up from start and come back, if pressure provided to wheel is elastic its punch up motion will increase power in system. For this time motion of both wheels will be powerful and speedy, that is punch up of wheel and rotation wheel. The motion can be used for vibratory and back and forth motion with frequency.

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